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SOLAR ENERGY FOR A CIRCULAR ECONOMY

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The vision of SUNRISE is to enable the production of renewable fuels, chemicals and materials on a global scale using abundant molecules as feedstocks (*e.g.*, H₂O, CO₂, N₂) and sunlight as the primary energy source. SUNRISE will develop artificial photosynthesis in a broad sense, aiming at solar to products yields tenfold to hundredfold higher than current biomass practice. SUNRISE will allow net-zero emission mobility and expedite the transition from a linear to a circular economy, with immense benefits for the society, the environment, the economy, and the ongoing efforts to mitigate climate change. The development of large-scale industrial processes employed in decentralized plants converting CO₂ into environmentally friendly long lasting (*e.g.* building) materials will lead to an important negative emission technology. SUNRISE will foster and rely on the development of energy-efficient disruptive manufacturing processes, sober in critical materials. The transition to a circular solar-powered society is a key step to preserve the biosphere and allow modern civilization to prosper. The key targets of SUNRISE on a 10-year timescale are:

- 2023:** Seasonal storage demonstrated with solar to chemical energy conversion better than 15%
- 2025:** Demonstrator at a scale of > 1 MW that will provide an urban environment with 10% of its energy in sustainable form, with CO₂ neutrality.
- 2027:** Demonstration of 80% circularity at the regional level with artificial photosynthetic technologies for industrial feedstock, products and processes
- 2029:** Negative emission carbon capture and utilization (CCU) and sustainable ethanol production on the industrial scale (*i.e.*, with concentration to the MW level)
- 2030:** 1000 ha (>150 MW) scale of SUNRISE technologies for liquid fuels production for, *e.g.*, air transportation
Decentralized and CO₂-neutral ammonia fertilizer production for precision farming

On a longer timescale, 2030 to 2050, SUNRISE aims at a CO₂-neutral economy with affordable negative emissions technologies on a significant scale.

LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CCU: Carbon Capture and Utilization
 DAC: Direct Air Capture
 EROI: Energy Return On energy Invested
 FT: Fischer-Tropsch
 ICE: Internal Combustion Engine
 ICT: Information and Communication Technology
 PEC: PhotoElectrochemical Cell
 PEM: Proton Exchange Membrane
 SOE: Solid Oxide Electrolysis
 STC: Solar to Chemical energy conversion efficiency
 STH: Solar to Hydrogen energy conversion efficiency
 TRL: Technology Readiness Level

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. SUNRISE concept.....	4
1.1 From The Fossil Linear Economy to The Solar Circular Economy	4
2. SUNRISE as a grand S&T challenge and game changer	5
2.1 S&T challenge	5
2.2 SUNRISE Goals and Approaches (in short)	5
2.3 Energy	7
2.4 Reducing Europe’s dependence on fossil fuels	8
2.5 New industrial opportunities for exploitation and sustainable development	8
3. SUNRISE Targets and Innovative pathways	9
3.1 Performance Targets	9
3.2 Quantitative Sustainability Assessment of SUNRISE technologies	10
3.3 ICT-based Materials Science	10
3.4 Innovation Process	11
4. The chemicals enabling the SUNRISE vision.....	11
4.1 Hydrogen (H ₂)	12
<i>Hydrogen today</i>	12
<i>Impact 12</i>	
<i>The targets for hydrogen production</i>	12
<i>Timeline</i>	13
4.2 Ammonia (NH ₃)	13
<i>Ammonia today</i>	13
<i>Impact 13</i>	
<i>The targets for ammonia production</i>	14
<i>Timeline</i>	14
4.3 Carbon-based Molecules (Cn) produced from CO ₂	14
<i>Artificial CO₂ fixation today</i>	14
<i>Impact 15</i>	
<i>Targets for artificial CO₂ fixation</i>	15
<i>Timeline</i>	15
A SUMMARY OF SUNRISE GOALS BY 2030 [in a box]	16
5. SUNRISE Goals and approaches	17
5.1 SUNRISE Goals	18
5.2 SUNRISE Approaches	18
<i>Approach 1 – Electrochemical conversion with renewable power</i>	18
<i>Approach 2 – Direct conversion via integrated artificial photosynthetic systems</i>	20
<i>Approach 3 – Direct conversion via biological and biohybrid systems</i>	25

1. SUNRISE concept

1.1 FROM THE FOSSIL LINEAR ECONOMY TO THE SOLAR CIRCULAR ECONOMY

Fossil fuels have had a tremendous impact on improving the quality of life globally during the last century. However, current production of fuels, plastics, agrochemicals, and pharmaceuticals based on fossil resources results in a linear economic model that is unsustainable, affects the stability of the biosphere, and causes anthropogenic climate change, thus threatening the future of modern civilization.¹ The phasing-out of this linear model in favour of circular economic innovations, which focus on the renewable use of resources, is no longer an abstract scientific ambition but a key objective of global political action under the leadership of the European Union (EU).

The only energy source that, in principle, can completely replace fossil fuels is sunlight. Even the most conservative estimates conclude that the flux of photons hitting the Earth is far in excess of modern civilization's energy requirements. However, the energy of incoming solar radiation must be harnessed and converted into a storable, transportable and recyclable form. The most effective strategy for doing so is the direct conversion of solar energy into fuels and chemicals (**solar fuels** and **solar chemicals**), *i.e.* storing energy in chemical bonds. A viable alternative to fossil carbon sources in the manufacturing of fuels and chemicals is currently the atmosphere itself, where anthropogenic carbon dioxide (CO₂) has accumulated, leading to global warming and the acidification of surface waters. Besides carbon, the atmosphere and hydrosphere are vast reservoirs of the other three main elements that feed the chemical industry: hydrogen, nitrogen, and oxygen. **The production of alternative fuels, commodity chemicals and materials from renewable energy, water, and atmospheric sources is a real game changer and one of today's greatest challenges.** While electricity is currently the main renewable energy carrier, it represents less than 20% of end-use energy consumption, with the rest being used in the form of fuels. In addition, the intermittency of renewable energy sources requires efficient and sustainable storage technologies in order to be competitive and attractive to energy companies. **SUNRISE is the large-scale initiative that will address these scientific, technological, and societal challenges through the photorecycling of atmospheric CO₂ into a variety of products and the photofixation of nitrogen to produce ammonia for fertilizers. More generally, closing loops at all levels, SUNRISE will make possible the direct solar-driven production of fuels, commodity chemicals or building materials.** The concept of SUNRISE is schematized in Fig. 1.

Fig 1. SUNRISE concept of a circular economy of carbon using solar energy input and atmospheric gases as feedstocks

¹ W. Steffen *et al.*, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **2018**, *115*, 8252; W. Steffen *et al.*, *Science* **2015**, *247*, 736.

SUNRISE is a game changer that will have an impact in many areas. These include:

- Establishing sustainable and efficient ways of storing intermittent energy fluxes
- Supporting a fully sustainable hydrogen and e-mobility for zero net emission transportation in urban environments
- Producing sustainable fuels, commodity chemicals and materials using the most abundant energy source, the sun
- Developing a sustainable CO₂-neutral air transportation system
- Restoring balance in the nitrogen cycle through precision farming via in-field and CO₂-neutral production of fertilizers
- Transforming the chemical industry with innovative strength for the manufacturing of sustainable new materials including biodegradable plastic substitutes and CO₂-storing building materials which we could call “artificial wood”
- Developing region-specific solutions to sustainable chemical production and energy storage
- Delivering less harmful fuels and chemicals for health and the environment
- Enabling a radical change in the energy system, *i.e.* from centralized to decentralized
- Transforming anthropogenic CO₂ into a valuable resource
- Accelerating the transition from a linear to a circular economy
- Reducing Europe's dependence on imported fossil resources and improving its energy security
- Developing the energy awareness of citizens in an industrial society

2. SUNRISE as a grand S&T challenge and game changer

2.1 S&T CHALLENGE

The unifying goal of SUNRISE is to **provide the key enabling technologies to make sunlight and ubiquitous molecules the prime sources of energy and materials for modern society, and displace fossil fuels by renewables on the terawatt scale.** This objective has far-reaching consequences with global significance, such as (i) mitigating global warming, (ii) promoting the transition to a sustainable circular economy, (iii) reducing the European economy’s dependence on energy and feedstock imports. SUNRISE thus addresses all three highly relevant issues simultaneously. Closing production cycles increases energy return on energy invested (EROI), is the optimal path for stabilizing and eventually reducing CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere and for decoupling the economic activity from depletion of natural resources. Furthermore it enables value creation from manufacturing renewables at a local level in a transaction economy that feeds into the economic system, thereby securing local energy supply, independent of imports.

The scale-up of current laboratory-scale solar energy conversion devices into widespread, efficient industry-grade systems and installations is a grand S&T challenge that requires both scientific and technological breakthroughs. The added value SUNRISE creates for European countries will be essential, since it will provide tailored solutions for each European region to achieve the optimal manufacturing strength from utilization of solar irradiance and site-specific resources.

2.2 SUNRISE GOALS AND APPROACHES (IN SHORT)

[see §5 for a more detailed presentation of SUNRISE approaches]

There are many different artificial approaches to producing chemicals from sunlight, ranging from electrochemical conversion to integrated photoelectrochemical cells and enhanced direct photobiological and biohybrid conversion systems (Fig. 2). SUNRISE will thus develop artificial photosynthesis in a broad sense, aiming at solar to products yields tenfold to hundredfold higher than today’s usage of biomass. To optimize yield, SUNRISE will promote knowledge exchange, interdisciplinarity and cooperation among relevant scientific and industrial communities, and foster hybridized solutions.

Fig. 2: Within SUNRISE, electrochemical conversion using renewable power in combination with electrolyzers will be complemented with photoelectrochemical and biological/biohybrid approaches for the direct conversion of sunlight into fuels, chemical compounds, and building blocks (www.sunriseaction.eu).

The transition from a civilization that is fossil-fuel-dependent to one that is solar-powered, and which uses ubiquitous and abundant molecules as feedstocks in a circular manner, is the grandest scientific and technological challenge of our times. Addressing such an enormous feat requires a multidisciplinary, intersectoral, and strongly coordinated effort. Urgent action is required: the latest IPCC reports² underline the need to reduce anthropogenic CO₂ emissions to below zero within 50 years in order to reach the ambitious goals of the 2015 Paris agreement. Technologies enabling such a transition are still in their infancy. Large-scale research and development efforts (from the megawatt scale onward) and massive investment are crucial. The enormous increase of wind and photovoltaic capacity in the EU and worldwide shows that a consolidated alternative to the use of fossil fuels on the terawatt scale already exists for electricity production.³ The situation is much less advanced for the conversion of solar energy into fuels and chemicals. Fossil fuels dominate transport and heating, with extensive existing infrastructure. The chemical industry, which supplies a variety of indispensable bulk chemicals, is dependent on fossil-based feedstocks. **Genuine manufacturing of concentrated energy carriers and sustainable feedstocks instead of extracting them from natural resources is a real game changer for today's energy system and the chemical industry.**

Table 1. Overview of SUNRISE Approaches and Goals. Present TRL levels are indicated. SUNRISE's ambition is to achieve TRL 9 for fuels and chemicals and at least 7 for CO₂ removal.

Approach	Present TRLs		
	Goal 1 Fuels	Goal 2 Chemicals	Goal 3 CO ₂ extraction and storage
1. Electrochemical conversion with renewable power fuels and commodity chemicals from CO ₂ , H ₂ O, O ₂ , and N ₂	3-8	2-4	0-3
2. Direct conversion via photoelectrochemical systems fuels and chemicals from CO ₂ , ... N ₂ and direct solar energy	2-4	0-3	0-3
3. Direct conversion via biological and biohybrid systems unconventional methodology for photochemical conversion of atmospheric CO ₂ with high yields	2-4	3-5	0-3

SUNRISE will undertake three approaches (see Table 1 and Figure 2) to delivering solutions on different timescales for the replacement of fossil resources. In the short term (2020–2025), we will focus on efficient

² Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, "Global Warming of 1.5 °C, an IPCC special report", 6 October 2018

³ World Energy Outlook, International Energy Agency, 2017.

and sustainable processes for the conversion and storage of renewable power into liquid or gaseous fuels, taking advantage of the continued growth of wind and solar electricity production. In the **medium term (2025–2030)**, we will forge tools to replace fossil feedstocks with key molecules and fertilizers produced with renewable energy. SUNRISE Goals (Table 1) will finally enable the Great Transition to take place on a longer timescale, deliberately reducing the level of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere (**2030–2050**). The ultimate long-term goal of SUNRISE is to outsmart nature in the use of direct sunlight (see Fig. 7, p. 17), capturing CO₂ directly from the atmosphere and replacing fossil fuels as carbon sources. SUNRISE will systematically identify and address bottlenecks that could prevent a meaningful implementation of its goals, such as the need to develop technologies with a high EROI (> 10) and to sustainably use critical mineral resources in the manufacture of conversion and storage devices.⁴

The above challenges require scientific and technological activities that are intrinsically multidisciplinary. Most notably, **the kind of revolution envisioned by SUNRISE in the field of energy conversion/distribution and industrial production will go hand in hand with profound changes in society, the environment, and employment.** More generally, the energy and industrial revolution enabled by SUNRISE will also result in a paradigm shift in the way we understand and organize the global economic system, demonstrating circular economy practices on a large scale, requiring active contributions from social, economic, and environmental sciences as well as the humanities.

Fig. 3 outlines the pathway of the great energy and industrial transition, which aims at securing climate stability over the course of the 21st Century. The pivotal role played by SUNRISE in this epochal process is evident.

Fig. 3 SUNRISE will provide the technological capability, with high energy efficiency, chemical yield, and materials efficiency, to displace fossil resources over time at an affordable cost and with acceptable land use.

2.3 ENERGY

SUNRISE aims to provide energy conversion technologies that comprise stable, long-term storage of intermittent, solar renewable energy in the form of chemicals. SUNRISE not only provides a sustainable alternative to fossil-based energy carriers, including energy storage for e-mobility, fuels for transportation (*e.g.* hydrogen, gasoline, diesel and jetfuel) and heat generation, but will also replace the energy-intensive fossil-fuel-based production of commodity chemicals. The long term target is making sunlight the sole primary energy source. In the shorter term, SUNRISE will increase the potential of e-mobility and hydrogen mobility, by providing higher efficiency and CO₂-neutral chemical storage solutions; SUNRISE will use renewable power, sunlight or electricity as an intermediate stage, to drive the production of fuels and chemicals from CO₂ point sources, and atmospheric water and N₂ by upscaling and innovating electrolysis (including the production of H₂ as an intermediate) and by implementing new catalytic reactions and processes. The production of CO₂ neutral jet fuels will be pursued by advanced biosynthetic or biohybrid processes as well as by integrating photo-electrochemical conversion and CO₂ Direct Air Capture (DAC) technologies.

⁴ N. Armaroli, V. Balzani *Chem. Eur. J.*, **2016**, *22*, 32.

Europe beyond 2050: 700 million people - 2 TW SUNRISE Power

Efficiency of solar conversion	Surface per capita	Total area needed	
100 %	30 m ²	0.3 %	
10 %	300 m ²	3 %	Artificial Photosynthesis
1 %	3000 m ²	30 %	
0.1 %	30000 m ²	300 %	Biomass

Fig. 4 Primary average power consumption per capita is remarkably constant at ~6kW for European citizens. The table shows the land area required for solar fuel production at different energy conversion efficiency levels. It is assumed that 50% of the ~6kW/capita must come from solar fuel, which is lower than the current level of 75% of primary energy for a European population of 700 million and average insolation of ~100 W/m². SUNRISE aims for 30% efficiency with an external quantum yield of 70%. This translates into ~100 m² per capita of surface required, which corresponds to ~1% of the European surface. This represents a massive leap forward compared to current biomass practice, which operates with less than 0.5% energy efficiency. This would require 10,000 m² per capita for the same amount of fuel and might well require more than the entire European surface to fulfil the needs of the population.

With technologies converting 10-30% of solar energy into energy carriers (see Fig. 4 and §3 and 4 for performance targets), SUNRISE is in a very good position to turn metropolises, towns and suburbs into massive environmental improvement machines on the surface they already cover, based on the excellent economic efficiency that can be obtained in densely populated areas and establish a new conditional growth mechanism as a driver for eco-modernisation.

2.4 REDUCING EUROPE'S DEPENDENCE ON FOSSIL FUELS

Europe depends significantly on imported fossil fuels, with more than 85% of crude oil and 70% of natural gas currently being imported from foreign countries.^{5,6} SUNRISE provides an alternative by replacing crude oil, natural gas, and other concentrated fossil-based energy carriers with sustainable fuels (including jet fuels) and commodity chemicals. The latter are produced using sunlight or renewable electricity and resources, which are abundant and ubiquitous. SUNRISE benefits from Europe's diversity and proposes a portfolio of solutions for each region, depending on the renewable energy sources available and on the economic environment. In regions with abundant renewable electricity (hydro, wind, solar,) and available concentrated CO₂ sources, electrolysis could provide a sustainable source of chemicals and fuels. In other regions with high solar irradiation, direct conversion approaches represent an ambitious, long-term option. With almost 75% of the European population living in urban areas, the importance of artificial photosynthesis for decoupling the economy from the consumption of natural resources cannot be overestimated.

2.5 NEW INDUSTRIAL OPPORTUNITIES FOR EXPLOITATION AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

In the short-to-medium term, electrolysis processes using renewable electricity and concentrated CO₂ sources will result in exploitation opportunities based on the replacement of fossil-based feedstocks with renewable commodity chemicals and the modernization of production processes. The newly developed technologies will allow industries emitting large amounts of CO₂ (*e.g.* cement manufacturing, iron- and steel-making) to reuse this greenhouse gas as a feedstock and remain competitive. The value for EU industry is evident also considering that Europe will become the leader for the global export of key industrial equipment in the energy and chemical sectors.

SUNRISE will propel Europe to a leading position in renewable energy and sustainable production. EU industry will depend less on imported fuels and will increase its competitiveness in a circular economic model. This, in turn, will facilitate industrial symbiosis, the development of smart cities and communities, and the deployment of innovative industry concepts. **New exploitation opportunities will emerge, especially for the materials and chemical sectors, leading to a complete modernization of industry, including new**

⁵ EU Crude Oil Imports and Supply Cost, Eurostat, 2018.

⁶ Natural Gas Supply Statistics, Eurostat, 2018.

catalysts, reactors, and processes. The sustainable and cost-effective electrochemical production of nitrogen-based molecules (fertilizers) and carbon-based fuels, and commodity chemicals will have a great impact on the chemical and transport sectors, respectively. The selection of novel commodity chemicals enabling the production of biodegradable and recyclable materials, including biodegradable plastic substitutes, with these new processes will also provide the European chemical industry with a tremendous innovative advantage in the pathway towards full sustainability. In addition, the advanced energy materials developed within the framework of the project will be of interest for other low-carbon energy technologies and will thus generate industrial opportunities in these areas. These include, for example, photosensitizers and light-harvesting materials for third-generation photovoltaics, new membranes for fuel cells, new catalysts and robust enzymes or strains for the chemical and biotech industry. SUNRISE technologies will also address the production of novel CO₂-storing building materials with the potential to revolutionize the construction sector.

3. SUNRISE Targets and Innovative pathways

3.1 PERFORMANCE TARGETS

In order to make disruptive energy conversion technologies environmentally sustainable, it is crucially important that energy return on energy invested (EROI) indices⁷ above 10 be achieved. Photovoltaic and wind technologies already achieve EROIs of about 15 and 20, respectively, whereas those of conventional oil and gas lie between 30 and 70, depending on various factors such as the geographical location of the extraction sites or the technologies employed.⁸ The EROI index of solar fuels is currently very low. To improve it, the energy conversion efficiencies of solar fuel devices must be significantly increased. With today's commercial technologies, overall sunlight-to-fuel energy conversion efficiency is only around 10% when using average commercial wafer-based silicon modules with a 17% solar-to-power efficiency, combined with electrolyzers and chemical reactors with a 50% power-to-hydrogen-to-hydrocarbons yield. Although this value is already significantly above that of natural photosynthesis (on average, < 1% of incident light converted into biomass), **SUNRISE aims for sunlight-to-fuel conversion efficiencies of at least 20% by 2025, aiming at 30% in 2030.** The short term goal could be achieved, for example, by 1) increasing the efficiency of photovoltaic systems to around 30% through the development of more efficient materials and device architectures (*e.g.* perovskites and highly ordered tandem solar cells), and 2) by raising the electricity-to-fuel efficiency to 80% using more efficient electrocatalytic hydrogen production coupled with downstream processes.

In the long term, SUNRISE will deliver technological approaches that convert solar energy and ambient CO₂ directly into chemicals. **Such a solar-driven chemistry represents a radical new form of energy and material conversion and storage.** SUNRISE aims to directly convert sunlight and small molecules into hydrogen, organic molecules (alcohols, hydrocarbons including aromatics), biodegradable plastic substitutes, fertilizers and CO₂-storing building materials. These radically new approaches include a range of new technologies from photo(electro)chemical processes to synthetic biology and biohybrid solutions. After 10 years, SUNRISE targets the ambitious goal of a 30% sunlight-to-fuel energy efficiency through direct photoconversion. The ultimate goal is the large-scale deployment of these technologies within a circular economic model, which will be implemented at all levels, all the way from decentralized devices to large integrated manufacturing plants and systems. SUNRISE aims for a sustainable CO₂ cycle, allowing for an initial decrease of CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere before maintaining it at a level compatible with climate stability. In line with a circular economy model, targeted products will include monomers for the synthesis of biodegradable plastic substitutes. The solar driven production of chemicals, including ammonia, must be associated with a smart (*i.e.* ICT-based) transport and concentration grid, for instance to deliver agricultural inputs in a precision farming approach. **SUNRISE will thus play a key role in enabling the shift to a carbon-neutral society, counteracting the effects of anthropogenic climate change.** For an effective impact on

⁷ Energy conversion efficiency is the ratio of the useful output of an energy conversion device (*e.g.* electricity) and the input (*e.g.* sunlight), in energy terms.

⁸ Photovoltaics Report 2019, *Fraunhofer ISE*, downloadable at www.ise.fraunhofer.de

negative emissions, bulk materials shall realise carbon storage for the very long run, either in the form of carbonates with a mineral base, or CO₂-storing building materials which we could call “artificial wood”.

3.2 QUANTITATIVE SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT OF SUNRISE TECHNOLOGIES

SUNRISE will enable the deployment of radically new energy and chemical production as well as manufacturing technologies, which comprise light-harvesting and integrated conversion systems on a large scale. This rapid pace of technology development requires the development of new analytical methods and computational methods (software) for the rapid assessment of the environmental, economic, and social impacts of these emerging technologies. New methods shall provide integration of these different points of views, with a particular focus on the impact on climate, which is the main incentive of SUNRISE. The climate benefit induced by the avoided CO₂ will be calculated, but also possible leaks of chemical compounds produced or used in the catalytic chains will be studied in terms of risk for climate, health and environment. For this assessment, as well as for integrated techno-economic and social studies, SUNRISE aims at cooperating with European centres focused on advanced methodologies. This effort will be essential to provide recommendations for SUNRISE technologies during development beyond the 1000 ha scale.

3.3 ICT-BASED MATERIALS SCIENCE

Novel materials will be crucial for achieving SUNRISE’s goals, because advanced materials are ubiquitous in the processes for the direct conversion of solar energy into fuels, chemicals and building materials. These include, for example, semiconductors, photosensitizers, catalysts, membranes and high-surface-area conductors, novel robust enzymes and microbial strains. Materials design and discovery is thus a cross-cutting key enabler for the entire SUNRISE technologies. However, translating new materials from the laboratory to the market can take 10 to 20 years and is very expensive, as highlighted by the Mission Innovation initiative.⁹ According to the Energy Materials Industrial Research Initiative (EMIRI), advanced materials denote 50% of the manufacturing costs of clean energy technologies today and are expected to increase up to 80% in the near future. Materials discovery crucially needs scientific breakthroughs to optimally design the matter from the atomic scale up to the device scale.

Catalyst materials, crucial in photo- and electrochemical approaches, also play a major role in the production of modern materials and components, reducing significantly the amount of energy needed to manufacture devices. Today’s catalysts have to be significantly improved and optimized in terms of efficiency and durability; they need to be earth-abundant and non-toxic in order to allow for a sustainable and affordable upscaling of the proposed technologies.

European solar fuel materials hubs – where equipment and knowledge at the forefront are concentrated – could provide an automation of experimental synthesis characterization techniques based on modelling, big data analytics and artificial intelligence, and relying on expanding European **high-performance computing (HPC) facilities**. Advanced computer simulation techniques additionally guide experimental developments. Millions of hypothetical materials can be explored through high-throughput calculations and the most promising candidates are selected using artificial intelligence. Computational studies provide fundamental understanding enabling rational design and accelerating the exploration, discovery and use of new high-performance, low-cost and non-toxic solar fuel materials.

Once efficient materials are found, they have to be integrated and tested under real device conditions and the nanoscopic scale has to be bridged to the macroscopic world, for example with new bio-inspired engineering theories mimicking biological design principles. New components, catalytic electrodes, reactors, as well as innovative designs, shall also be investigated, *in situ* and *operando*, with the most advanced analytical techniques available to find functional relationship of the structure, reactivity and transport properties. In SUNRISE, the integration of the most promising materials into devices and systems will be addressed, while considering all relevant scales and aspects, from the molecular level up to the device integrated within the entire system environment. **The final objectives are to optimize materials, device and systems architectures to achieve the highest possible solar conversion yield, and to scale up procedures for their**

⁹ Clean Energy Materials Innovation Challenge, Mission Innovation, 2018.

cost-effective production. Furthermore, eco-design principles and chemical processes for recycling materials and devices will be introduced without compromising the life cycle.

3.4 INNOVATION PROCESS

A critical step for disruptive technologies and the SUNRISE vision is to bring fundamental research to the market through the fastest possible route across "the valley of death" for commercialization. In part 4 (see below), the TRL outline for the production of target molecules is given in view of different possible technologies. As innovation is the sum of invention/fundamental research and commercialization, SUNRISE will also put emphasis on commercialization to push innovation forward. It is necessary to create an open innovation network of incubators, where new start-ups, spin-outs and spin-offs are embedded in the SUNRISE research infrastructure to accelerate raising the TRL levels from TRL 4/5 to 7/8.

To let the SUNRISE technologies evolve in a free environment, the concept of SUNRISE valleys (see Fig. 5) is introduced in the style of the recently launched Hydrogen Valleys¹⁰. To further realize this concept and to reduce the innovation cycle time demand, the combination of public funding drawn in from the green bond market as well as private investments and a long term commitment (10 years period) from the European Commission is crucial to engage private investments.

A comparable infrastructure of each valley concerning support with *e.g.*, bookkeeping, business angels, VC companies, IP support, lawyers, marketing experts etc. will enable the fast and focused development of technologies of the before mentioned fields of actions in a business-friendly environment. In cooperation with large industry, technologies can be distributed on a global scale.

SUNRISE will adopt best practices from other sectors/ economic regions for structuring the innovation process and for handling attendant information flow including intellectual property. We will leverage the existing Member State 'innovation infrastructure' to provide local nodes for assisting the overall Sunrise Innovation Process (SIP). Our SIP will be built up using well-recognised stages (outlined below). From the outset, it will be vital to create an innovation environment where contributors are purposefully exposed to the views and opinions of all stakeholders so that new concepts and approaches to converting sunlight into fuels and chemicals are in sync with the drivers that are shaping our societies of the future.

SUNRISE will bring together an Innovation team as part of, and reporting to, the governance structure. The Innovation Team will be specifically responsible for organising and running the SIP. The team will be expected to evolve with time to reflect new developments in the political and social European landscape as they happen. The team will be tasked with leveraging relevant resource, assistance and advice from local, national and European organisations and institutions in building the SUNRISE innovation nodes.

4. The chemicals enabling the SUNRISE vision

The SUNRISE vision is enabled by the sustainable production of key molecules: hydrogen (H₂), ammonia (NH₃) and carbon-based platform chemicals. The latter are made from both point sources and distributed sources of CO₂, the ultimate goal being CO₂ extraction from the atmosphere with subsequent storage. Fig. 6 schematically illustrates the production and final utilization of the SUNRISE enabling chemicals, which are manufactured thanks to solar energy

Fig. 5: Network of SUNRISE valleys in Europe. Geographical nodes shown are suggestions only.

¹⁰ Launched in March 2019 by EC Fuel-Cell & Hydrogen Joint Undertaking, in the frame of the Mission Innovation Challenge 8: Renewable and Clean Hydrogen. <https://www.fch.europa.eu/page/mission-innovation-antwerp-2019>

Fig. 6 SUNRISE simplified scheme of enabling chemicals production and usage

4.1 HYDROGEN (H_2)

HYDROGEN TODAY

The lightest chemical element is largely abundant on Earth, but mainly covalently bound to other elements. Molecular hydrogen (H_2) is scarce and is currently produced from hydrogen-rich molecules, primarily hydrocarbons (*e.g.* by steam reforming) and partly H_2O (by electrolysis). At present, major uses of H_2 include fuel refining, steel production, and ammonia production via the Haber-Bosch process.

IMPACT

H_2 is the most appealing and sustainable carbon-free transportation fuel solution for heavy-duty vehicles and personal long-range vehicles, equipped with fuel cells. H_2 is also a key process gas in chemical and heavy industry (*e.g.*, synthesis of ammonia and methanol, hydrogenation reactions, steel industry). Large-scale implementation of SUNRISE technologies with high STH yield will provide both short-term and seasonal storage of fluctuating renewable energy fluxes in urban zones. Moreover, a renewable H_2 economy can operate in both large-scale centralized factories and in small-scale distributed installations. As the latter will allow on-site production and deployment without the need for a complex distribution infrastructure, SUNRISE will provide decoupling of the economic activity from fossil resources in smart cities.

THE TARGETS FOR HYDROGEN PRODUCTION

H_2 production by electrolysis of water (“water splitting”) is already available today, but at high economic and material costs. Developing electrolysis routes to sustainably produce H_2 is high on the agenda of European and global stakeholders, federated in the Hydrogen Council and Hydrogen Europe associations. With the overarching SUNRISE goal of optimizing land use and maximizing material efficiency, and increasing the Energy Return On Invested energy (EROI), we target the large-scale production of H_2 by light-driven water splitting using novel photo-electrochemical cell technology, as well as innovations in materials to sustainably combine solar cells and electrolyzers. Solar H_2 can be used directly as fuel, as energy carrier to produce electricity via fuel cells, as an intermediary, often necessary step towards other molecules and as feedstock for industrial processes affording ammonia and carbon-based molecules such as ethanol.

SUNRISE will set up operational systems in rural areas at the area scale of hectares, producing H_2 (> 90 ton/ha·y) across Europe and further allowing the production of 300 ton/ha.y of ethanol (or equivalent carbon based fuels), or 500 ton/ha.y of ammonia at competitive cost levels starting from 0.4 €/l and down to 0.2 €/l for liquid fuel. To accelerate development of large scale systems, we will create local testbeds based on end-user volunteers. In addition to stimulating social acceptance, these small scale test-beds will provide data for

scale-up refinements. In 2030, SUNRISE H₂ production technology will represent a giant leap forward on the way to zero-emission mobility for people and transport, and net climate neutral feedstocks and material production in urban zones through processes that are at least 80% decoupled from consumption of natural resources.

TIMELINE

2021: Engaging the public in outreach activities, such as take-home experiments and demonstration of existing H₂ technologies, to increase awareness of the benefits of, and social acceptance for, solar-to-H₂ as a viable carbon-free energy option.

2025: Development of new materials for incorporation into electrolyzers (TRL3), for connection to commercial PV modules that employ abundantly available, non-toxic, and environmentally safe elements. Development of production-near manufacturing technologies for cost-efficient and robust processing of new materials.

Development of a scalable PEC device for direct light driven water splitting at readiness level 5, for H₂ production above 15% STH efficiency. The device will utilize abundant elements and provide >1 year stability. Benchmarking will be made against PV+ electrolysis systems.

Implementation of a steam generator with heat utilization in a first demo plant for a PV-SOE system with 20% STH.

2030: Reaching 30% efficiency in solar H₂ production, in devices employing scalable and environmentally benign materials, as well as cost effective and scalable manufacturing technologies

Infrastructural and technological development for conditioning, storage and distribution or direct reuse of H₂. Integration of H₂ production plants in the landscape, community and economy, via local testbeds. Implementation of solar H₂ production at the 150 MW range (500 resp. 1000 ha range at 30 resp. 15% STH). Coupling Solar H₂ production with NH₃, ethanol and jet-fuel production at the 150 MW range (TRL 9).

4.2 AMMONIA (NH₃)

AMMONIA TODAY

Worldwide food production nowadays critically depends on the use of industrial fertilizers. Ammonia is by far the most used one,¹¹ almost 90% of ammonia synthesized is applied in farmland, the rest is used for the production of chemicals (organic molecules such as amines). Ammonia is produced with the Haber-Bosch process using atmospheric N₂ and H₂ produced from fossil fuels and resulting in huge CO₂ emissions. The annual global production of NH₃ is > 150 Mton, along with >220 Mtons of CO₂ waste. In addition, the supply of fertilizers is currently inefficient with less than 40% of the nitrogen supplied as fertilizer being actually taken by cultivated crops. This results in large nitrogen-based pollution, with severe negative impacts on the environment and biodiversity. The nitrogen cycle is the most unbalanced cycle in the planetary boundaries analysis.

IMPACT

The industrial ammonia production, mainly *via* the Haber-Bosch process, consumes 3-5% of the world's natural gas supply, contributing to *ca.* 3% of the global CO₂ release into the atmosphere. Photo- and/or electro-catalytic reduction of atmospheric N₂ under mild process conditions, using H₂ from water splitting, will save a substantial amount of energy and will avoid CO₂ release. The switch from centralized to distributed on-site and on-demand NH₃ production from sunlight, air and water in rural areas will also result in savings of transport and storage related costs. Through limiting the amount of unused nitrogen fertilizer, we can further reduce the impact on the environment and biodiversity, and rebalance the nitrogen cycle. Beside its major use as a fertilizer, NH₃ can play a role as hydrogen storage material¹² and fuel. Indeed, conversion of air-abundant

¹¹World fertilizer trends and outlook to 2018, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2015

¹² Lamb, K. E., et al. (2019). "Ammonia for hydrogen storage; A review of catalytic ammonia decomposition and hydrogen separation and purification." *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 44(7): 3580-3593.

N₂ into nontoxic, safe nitrogen-based fuels such as aqueous urea ammonium nitrate, could provide comparable energy-returns to existing carbon-based fuels, but requiring lower energy for feedstock separation.¹³

THE TARGETS FOR AMMONIA PRODUCTION

Although the Haber-Bosch process now operates close to the thermodynamic limit in terms of efficiency, there is a need to develop efficient, sustainable and scalable processes that can operate at low temperature and pressure, to increase conversion. To achieve these goals, electrochemical and photo(electro)chemical catalysis are promising. A first objective will be the production of CO₂-neutral ammonia from atmospheric N₂ and solar H₂, using existing Haber-Bosch technology. On the longer run, we need to advance our understanding of biological N₂ reduction mechanism so as to first develop new homo- and heterogeneous electrocatalysts, photocatalysts and photoelectrocatalysts and then to integrate them into functional N₂ reducing systems driven by light or other renewable power. Direct and indirect (through intermediate production of solar H₂) co-(photo)electrolysis of N₂ and water should be considered.

These will allow for distributed ammonia production by converting atmospheric N₂ into NH₃ at ambient pressure and temperature. Within 10 years, SUNRISE will set up a pilot plant for decentralized solar ammonia production of 2 metric tons per day. In parallel, smaller systems will be developed, able to produce N-based fertilizers and to distribute them directly in the base of the plants in phase with culture needs.

TIMELINE

2021: production of CO₂-neutral ammonia from atmospheric N₂ and solar H₂ using existing Haber-Bosch technology.

2025: Developing electro- and photo-electrocatalysts able to convert N₂ to NH₃ (using electrochemical gas-phase conversion, photocatalytic N₂ triple bond cleavage, or any combination); Achieving selectivity between N₂ and proton reduction, using excited state properties and responsive matrixes; Ammonia synthesis prototype built for ambient condition operation (TRL 4).

Ready for operation plasma conversion prototype on a laboratory scale for the demonstration in a realistic environment.

2030: TRL6 electrochemical reactor for decentralized solar NH₃ production. The area claimed by the plant is smaller than 1 ha. The plant will produce 2 metric tons of fertilizer per day so that an agricultural area of 100 km² can be supplied with fertilizer with a density of 25 pound fertilizer per acre per year.

Autonomous solar-driven devices for decentralized (at the plant foot, in fields) NH₃ production for precision agriculture (TRL 5).

4.3 CARBON-BASED MOLECULES (CN) PRODUCED FROM CO₂

ARTIFICIAL CO₂ FIXATION TODAY

Low TRL technologies exist to turn CO₂ into carbon monoxide (CO) or formic acid with solar to chemical energy efficiency (STC) over 10%. Some catalysts are efficient and durable, but show a poor selectivity of products, except for CO and formic acid. Combining CO with H₂, or high-temperature co-electrolysis of CO₂ and water in SOE, produces syngas from which Fischer-Tropsch synthesis can be performed. Meanwhile electrolytic H₂ is being reacted with captured CO₂ in the thermo-catalyzed Sabatier process to yield methane. Molecules with two or more carbon atoms remain a challenge in (photo)-electrochemistry, as for Faradaic efficiency, selectivity and stability, although recent breakthroughs have been achieved for direct ethanol and ethylene electrocatalytic production from CO₂.¹⁴ Very few complete laboratory demonstrators have been reported. Reliable technologies have been developed to capture CO₂ from industrial flue gas, or directly from the air (DAC), but have so far not been combined with (photo)-electrochemical processes. By contrast, photosynthetic organisms can directly extract CO₂ from their environment, and photobiological processes exist for the production of alcohols, terpenes, jet fuels and high-value organic molecules that can be used as precursors for the synthesis of polymers and fine chemicals, including aromatics that can hardly be produced

¹³ Grinberg Dana, A.; Elishav, O.; Bardow, A.; Shter, G. E.; Grader, G. S., Nitrogen-Based Fuels: A Power-to-Fuel-to-Power Analysis. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2016**, *55*, 8798-805.

¹⁴ De Luna et al, *Science*, **2019**, *364*, 350

by heterogeneous catalysis. Hypotheses exist to enhance CO₂ conversion into molecules of interest in phototrophs exploiting microbial CCM (carbon concentrating mechanisms), increasing at the same time photobiological-driven CO₂ sequestering.

IMPACT

SUNRISE will provide carbon-based liquid fuels for jets and internal combustion engines (ICE) as the sole solution for a CO₂-neutral development of long distance air and sea transportation. 72% of the European population lives in urban areas that cover 17% of the surface, 4% cities and 13% towns and suburbs.¹⁵ The high yield solar-driven chemistry provided by SUNRISE will facilitate the full decoupling of the economic activity from natural resource consumption in smart cities. This will be a game changer in the decarbonization of Europe and its industry. New chemical synthesis routes will permit the transition towards CO₂-neutral biodegradable or environment-friendly materials, namely plastic substitutes and reinforcement fibers. Incorporation of carbon / CO₂ in building materials (artificial wood) able to store it for decades or even centuries, is indeed a main industrial concern, *e.g.* in the Cement industry. These are high on today's European agenda, with key European initiatives on the industrial side: Phoenix and the low carbon industry Strategic Value Chain worked out under European Commission leadership.

TARGETS FOR ARTIFICIAL CO₂ FIXATION

Carbon capture

SUNRISE will bring the energy efficiency to 70% of the thermodynamic limit at an affordable cost, by coupling DAC technologies with (photo)electrochemical conversion. By merging functions of electrodes or membranes with adsorbent materials needed to concentrate CO₂, we will cut losses for achieving a better economical and energetic yield.

Fuels, chemicals and materials

Although e-mobility and H₂-mobility are anticipated to take a large share of transport decarbonization, the availability of sustainable carbon-based fuels is considered indispensable for a CO₂ neutral long distance and aviation-based transportation system. ICE and jet fuels are priorities. Fuels for aviation will be obtained from biotechnological processes in the short to mid-term range, and later from a combination of solar-driven syngas production and Fisher-Tropsch processes. ICE fuels (*e.g.* ethanol) will be obtained either from (photo)electrochemical processes or via intermediate solar H₂.

Regarding commodity chemicals, ethylene should be obtained (photo)electrochemically, while synthetic biology is better fit to yield larger alkene derivatives, aromatics and synthons for *e.g.* biodegradable plastic substitutes and CO₂-storing building materials.

TIMELINE

In 2021, the result of "Fuel from the Sun" Horizon Prize will be known and used to refine the CO₂ to chemicals strategy.

2021: analysis of DAC technologies integration with SUNRISE electro- and photoelectrochemical approaches.

2025: Enhanced jet fuel production by biotechnological processes assisted by synthetic biology approaches, on the ha range with 40 tons/ha/y production target.

All-integrated PV+electrolyser for co-electrolysis of CO₂ and water, delivering liquid fuels/chemicals with a 15% STC efficiency.

The devices shall use flue gas from the industry, potentially the cement industry.

2030: deployment of 2025 device on the 150 MW scale (1000 ha at 15% STC), including DAC. This kind of devices will reach TRL 5-7 by 2030.

Reliable perspectives of large scale deployment shall be obtained, with anticipated price of this liquid commodities under 500 €/ ton. (about 0.4 €/l).

¹⁵ <https://www.pbl.nl/sites/default/files/cms/publicaties/PBL-2016-Cities-in-Europe-2469.pdf>

A SUMMARY OF SUNRISE GOALS BY 2030

The complete replacement of fossil fuels as the main energy and chemistry feedstock represents a paradigm shift that will require decades to be fully accomplished. In the next 25 to 50 years, mankind can make the transition to a system of technologies that will transform CO₂, H₂O, N₂, and O₂ into fuels and commodity chemicals, using sunlight as the only energy source. This process will radically alter the existing paradigms of industrial production and energy transformation and usage.

In order to kick-start this epochal transition of the industrial society and the global economy, the first ten years (2020–2030) are crucial, due to the need for a substantial acceleration in technological development². In terms of science and technology, SUNRISE will make Europe the global leader of this decade-long process by coordinating human resources, research infrastructure, and industrial know-how across the continent to accomplish the following goals by 2030:

- The use of CO₂, H₂O, N₂ and O₂, as feedstock to deploy solar energy converters that produce fuels (*e.g.* methane, ethanol, jet-fuels), synthesis gas (CO and H₂), commodity chemicals (*e.g.* ethylene, ammonia and biodegradable synthons for the plastic industry) and high-value chemicals at a groundbreaking level of over 100 ton/ha per year.
- The conversion of up to 2500 ton/ha per year of CO₂, depending on the molecular species and latitude, into the cyclic economic system.
- The enabling CO₂ mitigation strategies beyond 2050, when direct solar energy converters with a tenfold to hundredfold energy gain over the current biomass practice will be deployed worldwide on the TW scale for a negative-emission Earth system. This will allow for the production of long-lasting carbon based materials (*e.g.* ‘artificial wood’) for long-term carbon storage.

The key targets of SUNRISE on a 10-year timescale (and beyond) are:

2023: Seasonal storage demonstrated (*e.g.* a PV field >15 kW with e-fuel conversion) with solar to chemical energy conversion better than 15%

2025: Demonstrator at a scale of > 1 MW to provide an urban environment with 10% of its energy in sustainable form, with CO₂ neutrality.

2027: Demonstration of 80% circularity at the regional level with artificial photosynthetic technologies for industrial feedstock, products and processes

2029: Negative emission technologies for carbon capture and utilization (CCU) and sustainable ethanol production on the industrial scale (*i.e.*, with concentration to the MW level)

2030: 1000 ha (>150 MW) scale of SUNRISE technologies for liquid fuels production for, *e.g.*, air transportation.

Decentralized and CO₂-neutral ammonia fertilizer production for precision farming.

On a longer timescale, from 2030 to 2050, SUNRISE aims at a CO₂-neutral economy with affordable negative emissions technologies on a significant scale.

5. SUNRISE Goals and approaches

[This section contains a detailed presentation of SUNRISE approaches, already introduced in §2.2]

A realistic approach to SUNRISE's ambitious goals requires a thorough examination of the flux of solar photons that reach the Earth's surface and of the potential chemical conversion yields of these photons. Global irradiance on the ground varies continuously around an average value of 150 W/m^2 (mid-latitude average value: 180 W/m^2 see Fig. 7) depending on time, meteorological conditions, geographical location, and seasons. **The limits for candidate energy carriers are shown in Table 2, listing common half reactions starting from H_2 , CO_2 , and N_2 .** Estimates for CO_2 conversion and fuel production are obtained under the following assumptions: (a) systems absorbing 90% of the photons and converting 80% into products (SUNRISE target); (b) two photons per electron transfer; and (c) maxima and minima based on average annual solar irradiation in Malaga (Spain) and Stockholm (Sweden), respectively. The realization

Fig. 7 European solar irradiation map. For selected cities at different latitudes (Malaga, Piacenza, Warsaw, Stockholm) **the maximum potential for CO_2 conversion is shown in red circles**, together with the estimated production (per hectare and year) of a sustainable fuel (ethanol: green circles) or chemical (ammonia: blue circles). A two-electron process is assumed, consuming two photons per excited electron, 90% photon absorption efficiency and 80% chemical conversion efficiency. Radiation data for individual cities are taken from <http://wrdc.mgo.rssi.ru>.

of such targets on the hectare scale in rural areas or on a smaller scale in urban zones requires radical new concepts and tandem devices that operate on a laboratory scale with a photochemical current of 16 mA/cm^2 under AM 1.5 irradiation. The half reaction $n \cdot (\text{CO}_2 + 4\text{H}^+ + 4\text{e}^-) \rightarrow \text{carbohydrates} + n \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ also includes natural photosynthesis, with the additional restriction that it only uses half of the photons over the photosynthetically active region (PAR). Optimized biomass practice with *Beta vulgaris* L. (sugar beet)

Table 2. Selected half reactions for the conversion of CO_2 , H^+ and N_2 into chemicals and fuels. Minima and maxima refer to European regions with low and high annual solar irradiation. For details and assumptions made, see text.

Reaction	Conversion rate AM1.5 [$\mu\text{mol cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$]	CO_2 conversion potential [tons $\text{ha}^{-1} \text{y}^{-1}$]	Fuel/chemical production potential [tons $\text{ha}^{-1} \text{y}^{-1}$]
$2\text{H}^+ + 2\text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{H}_2$	0.086	-	52 - 130
$\text{CO}_2 + 2\text{H}^+ + 2\text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{HCOOH}$	0.086	1120 - 2800	1182 - 2956
$\text{CO}_2 + 2\text{H}^+ + 2\text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{CO} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.086	1120 - 2800	720 - 1799
$\text{CO}_2 + 4\text{H}^+ + 4\text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{CO} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.043	560 - 1400	386 - 964
$\text{CO}_2 + 6\text{H}^+ + 6\text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{CH}_3\text{OH} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.029	378 - 945	274 - 686
$\text{CO}_2 + 8\text{H}^+ + 8\text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{CH}_4 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.022	280 - 700	103 - 257
$2\text{CO}_2 + 12\text{H}^+ + 12\text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{OH} + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.014	378 - 945	197 - 494
$\text{N}_2 + 6 \text{H}^+ + 6 \text{e}^- \rightarrow 2 \text{NH}_3$	0.029	-	308 - 772

currently produces around 8 tons/ha of sugar and 5 tons/ha of ethanol annually through the direct conversion of atmospheric CO₂ to sucrose.

5.1 SUNRISE GOALS

The three SUNRISE Goals are: (1) the provision of sustainable **fuels** from renewable energy (solar fuels); (2) the synthesis of commodity **chemicals** from renewable energy (solar chemicals); (3) the development of efficient methods to **recycle CO₂** from the atmosphere (long term, 2050) (see Table 1). To fulfil these objectives, SUNRISE will pursue three Approaches beyond their current technological limitations, taking into account key bottlenecks such as EROI and the availability and durability of critical materials, warranting their scale-up at an affordable cost for materials and the Earth's surface. This synergistic approach gives SUNRISE an edge over the competition both within Europe and on a global level.

Table 1. Overview of SUNRISE Approaches and Goals. Present TRL levels are indicated. SUNRISE's ambition is to achieve TRL 9 for fuels and chemicals and at least 7 for CO₂ removal. [repetition of Table 1 in §2.2]

Approach	Present TRLs		
	Goal 1 Fuels	Goal 2 Chemicals	Goal 3 CO ₂ extraction and storage
4. Electrochemical conversion with renewable power fuels and commodity chemicals from CO ₂ , H ₂ O, O ₂ , and N ₂	3-8	2-4	0-3
5. Direct conversion via photoelectrochemical systems fuels and chemicals from CO ₂ , ... N ₂ and direct solar energy	2-4	0-3	0-3
6. Direct conversion via biological and biohybrid systems unconventional methodology for photochemical conversion of atmospheric CO ₂ with high yields	2-4	3-5	0-3

5.2 SUNRISE APPROACHES

As summarized in Table 1, SUNRISE will address its goals across all TRLs using three Approaches.

APPROACH 1 – ELECTROCHEMICAL CONVERSION WITH RENEWABLE POWER

The fastest-growing electricity generation technologies are photovoltaic (PV) and wind power, with price expectations below 0.03 €/kWh for the foreseeable future (IHS Markit, Aug 2018). However, this input must be integrated into the existing energy system, alongside distributed and dynamic chemical energy storage, with large-scale electrocatalysis providing a mature technology that can be rapidly implemented.

Fig. 8 The process chain for renewable power to hydrocarbons.

State of the art. Demonstration plants for power-to-hydrogen, power-to-gas, or power-to-liquid fuels by means of water electrolysis and subsequent thermal catalytic hydrogenation (*e.g.* Fischer–Tropsch) are currently being built on the MW scale; Fig. 8 schematically illustrates some examples. The energy conversion efficiency of commercial PV+electrolysis technology that can be deployed over large scale area is as high as 10%, using *e.g.* high-pressure electrolyzers and hybrid Si-based heterojunction solar panels. The cost for H₂ produced by a standalone PV+E system today has been estimated to about USD 10 kg⁻¹, ten times higher than the price of H₂ obtained by steam reforming natural gas, and twice the price of H₂ at a car fuelling station. The direct electrocatalytic conversion of CO₂ with Earth-abundant metals is a promising option that at present is at the lab research stage for both high-temperature (solid-oxide) and low-temperature (aqueous electrolyte and membrane-based) devices. The cost of electrolysis driven by intermittent power sources, with subsequent low-pressure CO₂ hydrogenation, is currently too high to be considered for practical use.

To make solar-to-H₂ and solar-to-fuels an economically attractive as well as environmentally and socially sustainable solution, SUNRISE will increase the energy conversion efficiency to 30% STH, in conjunction with lowered material and production costs by upcycling of waste streams. We will then showcase a system of distributed industrial production for a circular transaction economy, where value is created locally from CO₂ valorisation with an energy source characterized by distributed ownership (solar electricity) for industrial competitiveness. Already existing pilot plants will be taken as success stories to push the power-to-X technologies to the highest TRLs. Complementary to the existing processes, the gap of the production of jet fuels will be closed by the installation of the first of its kind demo plant using syngas or methanol as intermediates. We will also develop currently low-TRL electrocatalytic technologies for the synthesis of ethylene, propylene or ethanol from CO₂.¹⁶ Developing such new processes represents a real opportunity for targeting chemicals with minimized impact on the environment. They will use concentrated electricity with CO₂ from point sources or PV coupled with Direct Air Capture technology. The development of CO₂ capture technologies that can be directly integrated in electrochemical devices is another research direction that will be followed within SUNRISE. Finally, ammonia synthesis (Haber-Bosch process) uses 1-2% of the global energy supply and contributes to *ca.* 3% of the global CO₂ release into the atmosphere to sustain agricultural crop yield. With electrochemical technologies for nitrogen fixation, fertilisers can be produced locally, lowering the costs and risks associated with transportation of large volumes, and providing solutions to limiting the amount of unused nitrogen fertilizer to rebalance the nitrogen cycle. Combined with CO₂ activation processes, the electrochemical production of N-based chemicals as well as N-rich polymers and materials will be made possible.

Table of problems and solutions for approach 1

Bottlenecks	Research opportunities
Finding stable and abundantly available low cost catalysts for the water oxidation reaction. Key specification is the resistance to oxidative and acidic degradation ¹⁷	Alternative catalysts resistant to oxidative degradation (<i>e.g.</i> siloxanes, phosphates, polyoxometalates, and other main group oxides) will be used, supported by HPC, machine learning, and multi-scale modelling . Molecular knowledge (bioinspiration) will be transferred to materials science to integrate active catalytic sites within stable frameworks.
Development of selective and stable catalysts for multi-electron/multi-proton reductive processes for direct CO ₂ reduction and N ₂ fixation Tolerance of electrocatalysts to contaminated CO ₂ -feeds	High-throughput screening to discover materials coupled with experimental studies of catalyst design and function, thus opening up radical new avenues of electrocatalytic production for a whole range of platform products. Understanding degradation mechanisms (<i>e.g.</i> by multi-scale modelling). Strategies such as catalyst redeposition must be developed to keep the structure active. Develop smart matrices that can orient the selectivity and insure long-term stability as well as provide tolerance to O ₂ and other impurities/poisons.

¹⁶ Kätelhön et al. Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A. 2019, DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1821029116

¹⁷ Z. Seh et al., *Science* **2017**, 355, 146.

Scaling Solid Oxide Electrolyzers to MW size (<i>e.g.</i> limited reliability of cells leading to rejects in fabrication as well as failure in operation; cell performance enhancement necessary to minimize losses and required quantities of cells, thus, reducing cost; long term operation limited due to degradation by, <i>e.g.</i> catalyst migration, delamination...) requires producing several m ² of active area with high reliability cost-efficient production/stacking technology as well as low-cost housing materials	Increasing fracture strength and/or toughness by advanced materials, <i>e.g.</i> fiber-reinforcement, as well as utilizing proven mass scalable production technology being cost-efficient, <i>e.g.</i> tape casting, screen printing, deep-drawing, punching. High-throughput screening to discover high-performance materials with improved stability and tailored microstructures in order to improve performance, <i>e.g.</i> low electrolyte layer thicknesses, high electrode active surface areas. Understanding degradation mechanisms (<i>e.g.</i> by multi-scale modelling) and develop improved materials with low degradation and low contact resistance improving long-term performance.
Capital expenditure of electrolyzers (> 500 €/kW) are above the permitted range	Reduction of costs by material engineering towards cheap BOM (bill of materials) through the development of novel materials (<i>e.g.</i> ion-conducting membranes, catalysts) and novel architectures optimized by device simulation.
Tolerance of catalysts for thermal reduction of CO ₂ to feedstocks towards O ₂ and H ₂ O, improving selectivity	Structure–conversion correlations will be established by advanced structural and mechanistic analysis and catalytic characterization assisted by multi-scale modelling from the atomic scale to mass transport phenomena in order to enhance product selectivity in, for example, Fischer–Tropsch-type processes.
Low turnover/volume ratio of gas diffusion electrode-based CO ₂ and N ₂ electrolyzers	Design and simulation work will lead to scaling relationships being broken and higher currents being yielded (<i>e.g.</i> > 1A/cm ²) through alternative structural design, thus enabling, for example, a forced CO ₂ feed to the catalyst.
Electrolysis of diluted CO ₂ -feeds	Develop smart matrices that can adsorb CO ₂ selectively (separation from O ₂) and drive it to catalytic centers; Develop novel electrolyzers integrating CO ₂ -capture and conversion in one reactor. Redesign the materials systems of catalytic layers to implement CO ₂ -reducing catalysts with conductive support, ionomer for proton transport and channels for substrate/product transport.
Electrification of fine chemical synthesis (further conversion of bulk chemicals)	Develop and Design of new electrosynthetic processes to allow the further conversion of synthesised bulk chemicals for the production of various fine chemicals, pharmaceuticals, agro chemicals, etc.

APPROACH 2 – DIRECT CONVERSION VIA INTEGRATED ARTIFICIAL PHOTOSYNTHETIC SYSTEMS

SUNRISE pursues an ambitious vision of artificial photosynthesis becoming a truly disruptive technology to displace fossil fuels. Plant leaves and microalgae use sunlight to convert CO₂ into carbohydrates on the Gt scale every year with two photosystems acting in tandem. Direct solar conversion, often referred to as artificial photosynthesis, mimics this process in dual band gap nano(bio)structures (Fig. 9), combining and hybridizing the best knowledge of biological, molecular, and materials sciences. Approach 2 aims to develop such integrated photoelectrocatalytic arrays to enable disruptive technologies for renewable fuel and chemical synthesis from photoexcited states of materials and/or (bio)molecular material, thus directly driving catalytic transformations. This is potentially more efficient than the PV + electro(cata)lysis scheme developed in Approach 1. Classic electrochemical approaches use electricity as a reactant near chemical equilibrium with the excited state of the semiconductors in a solar panel, thus limiting the conversion efficiency. In Approach 2, the catalyst directly extracts charge carriers from the excited state of the photosensitizer to achieve multi-electron/multi-proton chemical conversion. A cascade of redox processes enhances quantum efficiency by separating charge carriers in space, thereby preventing recombination pathways. In other words, the entropy changes for the two (PV and electrolysis) steps are combined in the photoelectrochemical device to minimize losses, and the entropy can be used for the release of gaseous products such as O₂, H₂ or CO. This opens up the potential for high performance by high yield and overcoming intermittency of renewable energy input.

This leads to lower materials and systems costs than for Approach 1, which thus leads to better capital and energy return on investment.

In order to reach the high operational level of systems with 90% absorption and 80% conversion, SUNRISE proposes developing artificial photosynthetic technologies employing two tandem photosystems that will combine designed (supra)(bio)molecular and/or nanoscopic structures, aided by photon-management systems to maximize light harvesting. Natural photosynthesis is highly compartmentalized occurring in integrated multifunctional units that are composed of organized protein-based pigments, redox and catalytic cofactors. Such "quantasomes" are then multiplied in photosynthetic membranes.¹⁸ Exploiting photoactive biological membranes or component or applying the quantasome concept to artificial photosynthesis is a highly promising way to overcome the low efficiency and limited (photo)stability bottlenecks of existing model systems. Artificial quantasomes to be developed in SUNRISE will exploit recently discovered physical phenomena and emerging concepts of efficient light-harvesting, excitation energy transport, as well as ultrafast and directional charge separation by vibration-assisted coherent evolution of reactants into products and coupling between structural and electronic dynamics, plasmonic light-absorption enhancement and reactivity (plasmonic catalysis), quantum electrodynamic effects in cavities (strong photon coupling). In natural photosynthesis, light-activation of proteins is structurally controlled and the primary charge separation occurs as an ultrafast directional process with a near-unity efficiency owing to coherent coupling with vibrations of the protein matrix.¹⁹ Dynamic matrix response also directs electron transfer, stabilizes redox intermediates, drives charge separation to completion and prevents unproductive charge recombination. Driving photochemical reactions in a lossless non-adiabatic process converts energy with near-unity yield.²⁰ Vibration-induced delocalization between optically excited and charge-transfer states was also observed in synthetic materials.²¹ Coupling between the charge-separation process and dynamic matrix response emerges as a promising design principle (Fig. 10).²² Developing new selective catalytic sites for substrate (H_2O , CO_2 , N_2) reduction and coupled water oxidation, and their integration into photosynthetic membranes or artificial quantasomes will be essential, together with designing interfaces and couplings between the active components. Combining the quantasome and responsive matrix concepts in designing artificial photosynthesis systems will integrate the three fundamental losses of photocatalysis (originating from charge recombination, driving catalysis of product formation, and O_2 in only one potential loss. To achieve high efficiency, the primary light harvesting and ensuing charge separation need to be ultrafast; and the *de novo* design of supramolecular as well as inorganic responsive matrices and quantasomes is a formidable challenge and a key goal of the SUNRISE initiative.

Fig. 9 Schemes of possible architectures of tandem photoelectrochemical cells for solar fuel and solar chemical production. The inset exemplifies light harvesting with antenna effect, charge separation at the photosensitizer (P), and catalytic conversion in the case of H_2 evolution (Source: CEA)

¹⁸ Emerson, R.; Arnold, W. The Photochemical Reaction in Photosynthesis *J. Gen. Physiol.* Emerson and Arnold: The Photochemical Reaction in Photosynthesis 1932, 16, 191-205 and Park, R.B.; Biggins, J. Quantasome: Size and Composition *Science* 1964, 144, 1009-1011.

¹⁹ Romero, E. *et al. Nature* **2017**, 543, 355.

²⁰ T. J. Eisenmayer *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem B* **2013**, 117, 11162; D. Polli *et al.*, *Nature*, **2010**, 467, 440

²¹ Falke, S.M. *et al. Science* **2014**, 344, 1001

²² Bredas, J.-L. *Nat. Mat.* **2016**, 16, 35.

State of the art. The general idea of a compact, integrated device is an important driving force in the development towards sustainable solar-to-fuels. Direct solar-to-H₂ systems, including unbiased photoelectrochemical (PEC) cells, nanoparticle systems, and integrated PV-catalyst devices (so-called ‘artificial leaves’) have been demonstrated as lab-scale devices, with diverse materials and device architectures.²³ Semiconductor heterostructures and nanowire arrays for light-harvesting and charge separation have been integrated with catalysts for water oxidation and H₂ generation, and in some cases CO₂ reduction. Active photobioelectrodes combining biological light-harvesting modules with enzyme variant or synthetic catalysts have been reported. An artificial quantasome has been made and its water-oxidation demonstrated.²⁴ Many systems (such as photosensitized electrodes) operate well under diffuse light, making them suitable for mid- and northern latitudes of Europe. Enhancing light-harvesting efficiency by applying newly recognized physical concepts such as plasmonics, singlet fission, upconversion, and strong photon-matter coupling is currently an important direction of fundamental research in chemical physics. It is recognized that nano-structuring can improve light-capture and electron/hole collection efficiency. Low efficiency, which is sometimes caused by limited stability under solar irradiation, appears to be the main bottleneck of current systems of direct solar-to-fuels conversion. Many of the current challenges are similar between monolithic PV-catalyst and PEC solutions, such as achieving long-term catalyst stability, and tailoring the bandgap energies of the semiconductors/molecular photosensitizers used to both maximise solar utilization and operate at sufficient over-potential for catalysis to occur. The challenge of preventing recombination of charged intermediates in multi-electron photocatalysis is a specific challenge for PEC devices. Lab-scale demonstrations of monolithic PV-catalyst devices have currently reached close to 20% solar-to-hydrogen (STH) energy conversion efficiency in non-concentrated sunlight, albeit by utilizing rare and/or toxic elements, and materials that require expensive production processes.

In the SUNRISE project, we will change this situation by tailoring catalytic sites in advanced photoactive inorganic and supra(bio)molecular nanostructures exploiting or mimicking the functional compartmentalization of natural systems and optimizing the interfaces between light-harvesting, charge separation, and catalytic modules. Bottom-up supramolecular engineering of natural and artificial photosynthetic assemblies will be the key enabling technology in SUNRISE for developing the next-generation efficient solar-to-fuels energy conversion processes and systems. To achieve this, a robust function-based system engineering framework will be established for the design of artificial biomimetic systems that will aid in handling cross-scale models, identifying control points, and predicting system-wide effects of molecular components.

The research will be based on three guiding principles: (i) the integrated quantasome concept, (ii) vibration-assisted charge separation and transport involving coherence in responsive matrices, and (iii) kinetics synchronization and optimization between light harvesting, charge separation, charge-carrier transport, and catalytic conversion across interfaces. Semiconductor-based nanostructured photoelectrochemical systems (buried junctions, dye-sensitized n- and p- photoelectrodes coupled with catalytic sites...) will be developed as well, following similar design principles and sharing some of the catalytic units. The search for new materials will be guided by the computational and experimental screening of different elemental compositions. Semiconductor and catalyst development will be conducted in synergy with Approach 1, with the key challenge for Approach 2 being their integration.

SUNRISE will also consider enhancing light harvesting efficiency by employing newly emerging aspects of light-matter interactions: plasmonic enhancement of light absorption across the solar spectrum, singlet fission (to utilize high-energy solar photons while minimizing thermalization losses), up-conversion (to utilize

Fig. 10 Responsive matrices are chemically programmed for the high-yield conversion of reactants by conformational twisting along a quantum reaction coordinate (Q). An energy gradient drives the system through a conical intersection by means of a non-adiabatic (*i.e.* quantum coherent vibronic) process. Such reactions go beyond the Born–Oppenheimer characteristics of classic adiabatic photoelectrochemistry and (photo)catalysis.

²³ C.R. Cox *et al.*, *PNAS* **2014**, *111*, 14057; D. Jia *et al.*, *Nat. Commun.* **2016**, *7*, 13237; Q. Wang *et al.*, *Nat. Mater.* **2016**, *15*, 611

²⁴ Bonchio, M. *et al.* *Nat. Chem.* **2019**, *11*, 146

abundant low-energy solar photons), and the strong photon coupling regime (polariton formation in cavities) to facilitate light harvesting over antenna systems by accelerating excitation-energy transfer to reaction centers. Coupling between electron transfer and matrix dynamics will be utilized to accelerate and direct the initial charge separation and charge-carrier transport to catalytic sites (coherence-driven and nonergodic electron transfer). Photosynthetic systems will be kinetically optimized, while minimizing recombination reactions that both limit the performance and can lead to material degradation. Improved stability will thus be an emerging property of the device. Integration of active components into functional compartmentalized units (quantasomes) will be a challenge requiring us to design active interfaces to provide controlled electronic coupling, proton transfer, and mass transport (reactants, products).

Bioinspiration will be the key driver of Approach 2. We will target materials, which (i) are based on Earth-abundant elements, for reasons of cost-effectiveness and possible global upscaling, (ii) have catalytic sites with very few metal ions (in comparison, only a small fraction of metal atoms in nanoparticle catalysts are surface-exposed and thus catalytically active), (iii) are highly selective and efficient in terms of energy conversion, and (iv) operate under ambient temperature and pressure conditions in aqueous media, thus reducing the environmental impact of manufacturing processes (*i.e.* green, safe processing).²⁵ Biomimicry of the active sites of metalloenzymes (hydrogenases, dehydrogenases, nitrogenases, laccases, *etc.*) will be used to design new catalysts for multi-electron/multi-proton reactions such as CO₂, O₂ water, and N₂ activation. (Supra)molecular and inorganic nanoparticle catalysts will be used, in combination with hybrid "matrices" and membranes, building on the current state of the art to control light-harvesting, charge separation, and catalysis. Photoactive bio-components (isolated photosynthetic reaction centers, photosynthetic membranes, redox cofactors) will be assembled with enzymes and synthetic catalysts in hybrid structures to enhance direct conversion processes. Photodriven catalytic protein systems ("photoenzymes"), which will combine photoreducing (or photooxidizing) and catalytic sites within a protein matrix will be investigated, developed, and explored. Mutants of natural redox proteins and enzymes with increased functionalities as well as *de novo* protein platforms, will be combined with photosensitizers or biological light-harvesting modules. Such artificial systems will allow for the efficient coupling of light harvesting and catalysis as well as the rapid separation of the products. Proteins also appear to be the first choice for responsive matrices, together with synthetic supramolecules, hybrid or inorganic membranes, and polymers. QM/MM/MD simulations and materials-oriented HPC will aid predicting functional materials, photoenzymes, and their assembling in artificial quantasomes. SUNRISE will also study and explore self-assembly, self-repair, and regulation of photosynthetic assemblies to gain a better understanding of how they create energy gradients, boost catalysis, and maintain integrity. These accomplishments will enhance efficiency (improvement of light-harvesting properties, optimization of electronic connection between photosensitizer and catalyst) and also address stability (development of smart matrices and protective coatings, disarming of triplet states and reactive oxygen species, and self-repair/self-healing mechanisms). Resulting functional direct-conversion devices will most probably be hybrid systems combining supra(bio)molecular quantasomes with nanostructured materials (semiconductors, 2D-materials, possibly 3D covalent organic frameworks and metal-organic frameworks), and/or with novel systems obtained through synthetic biology.

H₂O and CO₂ will be used as feedstocks for artificial photosynthetic systems, producing hydrogen, methane or syngas as 1st generation solar fuels and formic acid as 1st generation solar chemicals. Water oxidation should be coupled with fuel production, while alternative oxidative processes will be developed for the production of commodity chemicals (*e.g.* H₂O₂, epoxides) Based on the progress made in Approach 1, we will subsequently develop artificial photosynthetic systems that produce more complex solar fuels, solar commodity chemicals (*e.g.* ethylene, ammonia), and high-value compounds. This will align with recent advances with respect to photoredox catalysis in synthetic organic chemistry and will drive the transition to more sustainable, minimal waste, and circular chemical manufacturing processes.

²⁵ V. Artero, *Nat. Energy* **2017**, 2, 17131.

In terms of the technological readiness, further development and integration with Approach 1 – systems into single photosynthetic units (buried junctions, sensitized photoelectrocatalysis) can be developed into applicable stage (TRL 6-8) within the next 10 years. *De novo* (*i.e.* contingent) systems engineering with bioinspired (bio)molecular-based modules utilizing the quantasome concept and novel physical principles to facilitate light harvesting, charge separation and transport present a major scientific and technological challenge and will lead to the next generation of artificial photosynthesis. TRL 4-5 is achievable in 10 years, provided that the corresponding development is supported by a critical mass of fundamental work that is genuinely cross-disciplinary across biology, chemistry and physics.

Table of problems and solutions for approach 2

Bottleneck	Research opportunities
Low conversion efficiency and stability of direct-conversion systems	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Increase light harvesting efficiency, charge-separation and catalytic conversion yields by biomimicry and employing new physical concepts (coherence, responsive matrices, singlet fission and upconversion plasmonic, strong photon coupling) 2) Apply the quantasome concept to integrate light-harvesting, charge-separating, and catalytic sites, organized and responsive matrices in functional units 3) Enhance inherent robustness by facilitating productive steps, combine with self-repair processes.
Sunlight harvesting not sufficient in meeting the 90% absorption target across the relevant part of the solar spectrum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Photon management in photosynthetic systems: singlet fission and NIR photon upconversion to utilize high- and low energy solar photons, plasmonics to enhance absorption in visible region -exploit biological light-harvesting modules with increased absorption cross-section - Multichromophoric antennas, use delocalized excitons - Facilitate excitation-energy collection and its channeling to charge-separating sites or heterojunctions by employing strong light-matter interactions (polaritons) - Spectrum-splitting ("Z-scheme" systems).
Inefficient charge-separation due to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - charge recombination - side reactions, charge trapping, excited-state decay - kinetics mismatch between charge transport and catalytic conversion 	<p>"Electron transfer beyond Marcus theory":</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Utilizing hot excited states - Coupling electron transfer with matrix dynamics: nonergodic electron transfer, non-adiabatic conversion by adiabatic passage (NCAP), polaron-stabilization of charge-separated states - Coherence-driven electron transfer (directing and accelerating) - Charge separation directly from excited light-absorbers (avoiding antenna-to-reaction center energy transfer) - Integrating charge separation and catalysis in quantasomes.
Slow catalysis, poor selectivity, catalysts cost and availability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New catalysts capable of multielectron/multiproton transfer, charge-carrier accumulation - genome mining for novel robust enzymes - "photoenzymes": synthetic photocenters and catalytic sites in a protein matrix - Responsive matrices to fine-tune proton-coupled ET - Plasmonic catalytic or electrocatalytic systems utilizing plasmon-generated hot charge carriers and electromagnetic near-fields, integrating light absorption and catalytic action - Photochemistry of earth-abundant elements - based photosensitizers that operate at moderate pH - Controlling and optimizing traffic of substrates and products.
Recombination, at the semiconductor/catalyst interface, and in the bulk, limits efficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engineering semiconductor/catalyst interfaces to allow for rapid adaptation of catalyst potential with the Fermi level of the semiconductor - Developing electron buffer materials to induce charge accumulation at high and low electrochemical potential

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Kinetics optimization of electron-transfer pathways between charge-separating and catalytic sites in supramolecular as well as sensitized electrode and nanoparticle interfaces - oriented immobilization and nanostructuring of photoactive and catalytic modules with respect to electrode surfaces to minimise back reactions.
Poor cofactors integration into functional systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Compartmentalization based on replicated quantasomes - Membrane and responsive matrix design - Engineering of electron-, proton- and energy transfer pathways between cofactors - Combining supra/bio/molecular systems with structured semiconductor surfaces, nanostructures, 3D or 2D-materials, optimizing interfacial processes - Efficient and stable grafting strategies.
Limited (photo)chemical stability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increasing rate and directionality of primary charge separation - Improving catalyst selectivity - Compartmentalization (employing the quantasome concept) - Self-repair mechanisms - Stabilization by interfacial charge separation at semiconductor surfaces - Build-in disarming of reactive side products (ROS, O₂ shielding, organic triplet states) for photoprotection - exploring novel robust redox enzymes (through genome mining) and genetic engineering of the existing redox enzymes to improve their stability.
Instability of semiconductors in the presence of aqueous electrolyte	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using HPC and modelling to develop protective/passivating strategies as well as optimizing kinetic stabilization. - Implementing self-healing and optimizing kinetic stabilization.
Photocatalytic back reactions destroying the generated products	Axiomatic design (theory and application) systems engineering of smart and responsive matrix architectures with differential affinity for reactant and product.
Leaching of photoabsorbers or catalysts during operation	Developing specific matrices in all-solid-state configuration to recapture these key components from the electrolyte or implement self-healing processes.

APPROACH 3 – DIRECT CONVERSION VIA BIOLOGICAL AND BIOHYBRID SYSTEMS

SUNRISE will employ two different types of systems – biological and biohybrid– which both involve living microorganisms and are capable of direct solar energy conversion and storage. In SUNRISE, different variants of explicit biological or biohybrid systems and microbial co-cultures will be exploited.

State of the art. The photosynthetic organisms use sunlight as energy source and raw materials such as CO₂, water and/or N₂ and some mineral nutrients for synthesis of various molecules. Photosynthesis allows application of algae and cyanobacteria for industrial production of different natural products using exclusively sunlight and CO₂ (e.g. industrial production in Europe [Ecoduna](#), [Algaenergy](#), [Algosource](#), or in Japan [Euglena Co Ltd](#)). Dozens of engineered photosynthetic organisms hosting novel synthetic production pathways and enzymes are currently available. Yet, all the available prototypes

Fig. 8 Schematic representation of solar fuel and chemical production by photosynthetic microorganisms (living factories) (A) and by a biohybrid system comprising a man-made inorganic photosensitizer powering the fuel and chemical synthesis in heterotrophic bacteria (B).

have a low solar-to-chemicals conversion efficiency and need significant improvements to serve as industrial-scale production platforms. Exploitation of photosynthetic microorganisms to function as *microbial cell factories*, which catalyze the entire and direct process for production of solar fuels and chemicals, is becoming a reality along with development of strong synthetic biology technologies. Advanced and automatized synthetic biology toolboxes are currently becoming available at the advanced level for heterotrophic (non-photosynthetic) microorganisms systems (bacteria and fungi). Radical progress in development of synthetic biology tools also for photosynthetic microorganisms now opens great prospects for realisation of algal/cyanobacterial-based direct production of renewable and sustainable chemicals. Photosynthetic light-driven biotransformation by coupling specific redox enzymes (*e.g.* oxidoreductases) to light reactions provides a great potential for serving green chemistry by enabling a sustainable production of a wide range of desired bioproducts. The advantages of whole-cell biotransformation over the use of many industrial chemical catalysts, include the high selectivity, shorter synthetic routes, reduced toxic by-product formation and operation under physiological conditions. The proof-of-the concept for the ‘substrate in – product out’ photosynthetic biotransformation has been recently demonstrated, yet, the efficient and continuous platform requires further development.

The choice of the starting chassis and novel enzymes for photosynthetic cell factories is of critical importance in industrial platforms. Out of the thousands of known species of algae/cyanobacteria, only a few strains are currently being employed as a production chassis. Research must focus on *selecting robust strains* capable of high biomass yield in industrial mode of cultivation but also being equipped, with favourable metabolic characteristics.

The economic feasibility of the *microbial cell factories* technology still suffers from inherent problems of solar-based aquatic production systems, such as self-shading (leading to low light utilization and low production efficiency), excessive water consumption and requirements for energy-intensive mixing. Prolonged life time (*e.g.* avoiding the degradation of lipid reserves during the night) and optimization of secretion and separation of fuels and chemicals are also mandatory for biocatalysts to perform efficiently in photosynthetic cell factories.

There are already >> 30 successful **proof-of-concept** reports for direct production of a plethora of fuels and chemicals, including hydrogen, alcohols, diols, polyols, alka(e)nes, fatty acids, organic acids, terpenoids etc, using cyanobacteria or microalgae as host organisms. These systems and chemical production platforms will be further improved by the proposed SUNRISE technologies. Currently there are several small companies in Europe (*e.g.* [Photanol](#)) working towards SUNRISE objectives for demonstration of the economic viability of the specific direct production platforms within photosynthetic microorganisms. The technology with best production yields for specific chemicals (*e.g.* lactic acid in Photanol) is currently at TRL 4 using pilot system enclosed in a greenhouse environment, but with plans and funding to build an outdoor demo plant to run at TRL 7. SUNRISE will strongly boost the speed of increasing the TRLs of several different target production systems that now are at a proof-of-concept stage. Ongoing collaborations and joint research programmes already exist between SUNRISE and oil/ and gas companies, (*e.g.* Total) to accelerate progress on the selection and optimisation of microalgae strains for industrial application²⁶.

Biohybrid systems involve a material–microorganism interaction. They generally rely on the best man-made systems for solar energy conversion and provide this energy as reducing equivalents in a suitable form (*e.g.* electrons or H₂) to drive biosynthetic pathways in non-photosynthetic microorganisms, thus ensuring the direct, integrated solar-driven production of desired target chemicals and fuels. Proof-of-concept experiments were recently presented with integrated systems whereby microorganisms metabolize H₂, formed by *in situ* photoelectrochemical water splitting, to drive CO₂ fixation and production of, for example, large alcohols with promising H₂-to-alcohol conversion efficiencies. In other systems, bacteria or archaea feed directly on electrons produced by light-harvesting semiconductors and produce ammonia, methane or a variety of larger carbon compounds.

²⁶ <https://www.total.com/en/energy-expertise/projects/bioenergies/pcv-algaeparc-qibebt-proving-and-harnessing-microalgae-potential>

In the SUNRISE project, the reducing power produced in the light reactions of photosynthetic microorganisms or in the man-made solar conversion devices of biohybrid systems will be efficiently coupled to maximize the CO₂ reduction capacity and the production of high-density, complex carbon products in microbial cells.

The biological production systems with photosynthetic microalgae or cyanobacteria as host organisms will be designed to function as living photosynthetic microbial cell factories that channel the maximum share of available resources (solar-based reducing equivalents and CO₂) for the production of target chemicals, while maintaining a minimal flux for necessary housekeeping functions and other cellular activities. Target products are either volatile or engineered to be stored in or “pumped” out of the cells in order to maintain the high-level strength of the intracellular electron sinks. Photosynthetic microbial cell factories will be designed and tailored with advanced synthetic biology tools. They will also be guided by interactive models, enabling maximal solar energy utilization for CO₂ reduction in every single cell for the high-yield synthesis of specialized products. Photosynthetic living factories will have also to grow on fresh, saline, and wastewaters, thus promoting a circular economy and ensuring a low impact on agriculture and arable land use.

SUNRISE will make use of extensive research on synthetic biology and metabolic engineering for a wide range of production pathways in model organisms, taking into consideration the holistic function of the host organisms on the production system. The project will also develop attractive industrial biotechnology platforms for direct solar energy storage in a wide range of renewable fuels and chemicals. Systems biology and physiological knowledge of cyanobacteria and green algae has significantly advanced over the past 20 years, hence SUNRISE can opt for the best strain selections and commercial production systems for its synthetic biology approaches.

Research into biohybrid systems for the direct conversion of solar energy, water and CO₂ into a wide range of products has only just begun but is highly promising if the key issues, such as long-term stability, can be resolved. SUNRISE will boost the development of biohybrid methodologies to create stable and viable bionic systems. This includes the construction of optimized interfaces between living systems and materials, solving the issues of importing non-biological material into cells, the possible impact of non-biological material on the metabolism, and the toxicity of the non-biological material for the cells.

In SUNRISE, advanced photobiological and biohybrid systems will be primarily employed for the production of complex molecules such as hydrocarbons (fatty acid, alkanes, terpenes and jet-fuels.), aromatics (as synthons for fine chemistry and production of artificial wood), and precursors for biodegradable plastic substitutes.

Table of problems and solutions for approach 3

Challenge	Research opportunities
Efficient production of photosynthetic reducing equivalents (Fd, NADPH, electrons and protons) and their coupling for bioproduction	Improvement of photosynthetic linear electron transport for efficient and homogeneous light harvesting and utilization in industrial-scale applications. Efficient coupling of reductants (i) with redox enzymes for a direct synthesis of targeted chemicals (including photobioproduction of H ₂) <i>in situ</i> and (ii) with novel enzymes or engineered bacteria in the electrochemical devices. Minimize inhibition and damage of biocomponents.
Efficient coupling of harnessed solar energy with CO ₂ reduction pathways in microorganisms and in biohybrid electrochemical devices	Enhanced carbon-concentrating mechanisms and CO ₂ fixation, either by natural pathways or by introducing novel pathways by utilizing synthetic biology tools. Metabolic engineering of efficient “electron sinks”, and elimination of competing metabolic pathways. Maintain a balance between production of photosynthetic reducing equivalents and ATP. Construction of optimized interfaces (on metabolic and material design level) between biocomponents and materials to ensure efficient electron transfer either via direct electron transfer or via electron mediators such as H ₂ . In order to achieve this an improved understanding of cathodic external electron transfer pathways and/or hydrogen metabolism is required.

Broadening the light-harvesting spectrum, optimizing light harvesting.	Utilization of sunlight across the entire PAR down to far-red region through the innovative use of natural and synthetic pigment systems. Application of plasmonics to boost functionality of (bio)catalysts. Minimize energy waste by lower useless light energy dissipating mechanisms.
Identification and selection of robust host organisms (chassis) and enzymes	Exploit biodiversity to select new strains with O ₂ tolerant enzymes and enhanced robustness towards industrial productivity (enhanced biomass, NO _x and SO _x resistance, tolerance of elevated growth temperature and illumination, withstanding high CO ₂ concentrations etc). Make use of natural biodiversity (genome mining) including identification of novel robust enzymes. Application of the adaptive laboratory evolution approach to select production organisms/enzymes with improved desired functionalities.
Improvement of the synthetic biology toolboxes, and rapid engineering of libraries of strain variants.	Computational design using HPC and reconstruction of metabolic models for selected production strains. Reiterative quantum modelling of electron-transfer processes including competing pathways. Design novel production pathways with strict cofactor balancing of the reactions and pathways, resulting in improved carbon yields. Automatization of synthetic biology processes. Systems Biology and ‘omics’ technologies to understand complex biological networks and systems.
Durability and lifetime of the microbial cell factories and biohybrid devices	Enhancement of durability and lifetime by optimizing biocomponent/synthetic material interfaces. Improvement of the longevity of host organisms by systems biology and physiological monitoring, with subsequent alleviation of constraints developed, and by investigating microbial co-cultivation opportunities. Elimination of toxicity of end-products and non-biological materials. Optimization of the import of external substrates and export and separation of products. Taking into account the reproduction of living cells.
Photobioreactor design	Apply engineering skills and machine learning for optimization of photobioreactor design in terms of light harvesting as well as product biosynthesis and collection. Successful up-scaling and valorisation of large-scale production platforms.

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